

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Improving Document Element Detection Through Single and Two Stage Model Integration

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Abstract

Objectives: This study focuses on developing a hybrid detection model that can improve document element like signature detection, by combining single-stage and two-stage object detection architectures. The objective is to improve the detection of objects with higher processing efficiency. **Method:** YOLOv8n is used for fast and real-time detection, and Faster R-CNN is used for accurate classification. Post-processing method: The approach involves the combination of predictions with their respective confidence scores and IoU values. **Findings:** The overall model is more accurate with average precision of 100.00%, recall of 92.15%, F1-score of 95.74%, IOU of 76.29%, and Dice co-efficient of 83.77% than the individual models, especially for challenging document categories. **Novelty:** This work introduces a new custom dataset and the presentation of a hybrid detection model that combines YOLOv8n and Faster R-CNN for improved document element detection. In this proposed system, instead of relying on either a speed-optimized or accuracy-optimized model, the proposed system combines fast initial detection with region-based refinement in a single model. The proposed system is particularly beneficial for semi-structured document organization and can be applied to real-world signature detection problems.

Keywords: Document Element Detection; YOLOv8n; Faster R-CNN; Hybrid Model; Signature Detection; Object Detection

1 Introduction

Signature detection has emerged as a prominent area in document processing, especially in industries that are heavily dependent on official documentation, such as banking, law firms, government agencies, and educational institutions. Stamps, verification signs, and most importantly, handwritten signatures, act as crucial authenticity markers and play a pivotal role in combating fraud. However, with the advent of deep learning and computer vision, there has been tremendous growth in the development of intelligent systems capable of performing intricate recognition tasks such as object detection, handwriting recognition, and medical image analysis. In document processing, these

advances have enabled the performance of automated verification, fraud analysis, and mass digitization to be done in a more efficient and less labor-intensive way.

The earlier heuristic and template-based approaches have been largely susceptible to inconsistencies in the document layout, structure, and noise while scanning. In contrast, deep learning-based detection techniques have shown improved accuracy, robustness, and flexibility, and can handle higher levels of automation. However, each of the detection methods has its own trade-offs. One-stage detectors such as YOLOv8n (You Only Look Once) are able to perform fast detection, which is quite useful for real-time systems but may not be the best for accurate localization in complex environments. Two-stage detectors such as Faster R-CNN (Faster Region based - Convolutional neural network) are able to perform accurate localization and classification but are computationally expensive and slower. The trade-off between speed and accuracy makes it the need of the hour to have a balanced framework that can capitalize on the benefits of both. Recent studies have therefore attempted to design hybrid pipelines, multi-scale feature fusion, and refinement methods to enhance detection accuracy in complex visual environments. On the basis of these developments, this paper proposes a hybrid detection framework that combines YOLOv8n with Faster R-CNN to enhance document element detection.

The primary aim of this research work is to achieve a balance between the speed of detection and the accuracy of localization. The proposed system aims at the detection of handwritten signatures in semi-structured documents, which is a crucial step in cheque authorization, certificate validation, invoice approval, and administrative record verification. The proposed system utilizes the advantage of YOLOv8n in fast localization and the refinement process of Faster R-CNN to improve the detection accuracy and facilitate efficient document automation.

Several research papers have contributed to shifting the boundaries of signature and document element detection⁽¹⁾. R-CNN-based methods have proved that handwritten signature regions can be efficiently detected even in complex layouts⁽²⁾. Benchmarking methods for Chinese documents covered signature detection, restoration, and forgery verification, with F1-measures over 90%⁽³⁾. Automated cheque verification systems successfully extracted handwritten information, stamps, and signatures with 94% accuracy⁽⁴⁾. Hybrid approaches that combined CNN and HOG features enhanced signature classification to 92.6%⁽⁵⁾. Real-time detection models have also been enhanced. Light models of YOLOv8 reached over 60 FPS with 88% accuracy in embedded document scanning tasks⁽⁶⁾. YOLOv9 brought programmable gradient optimization, which boosted accuracy by 3% compared to YOLOv8, and⁽⁷⁾ YOLOv10 optimized the whole processing pipelines to decrease latency⁽⁸⁾. YOLOv11 brought feature pyramids and attention mechanisms, which significantly enhanced the detection accuracy of small or contrasted regions of documents with 93.2% accuracy and 91% precision. The methods based on segmentation also showed high accuracy in pixel-level document detection⁽⁹⁾. The models of Mask R-CNN showed high-quality segmentation of the areas of stamps and signatures with IoU 0.87 and pixel accuracy of 90%.

Other real-time monitoring tasks proved the universality of contemporary detection models. In⁽¹⁰⁾, proposed a real-time face mask detection system with 98% accuracy and F1-score. In⁽¹¹⁾, designed a CNN-based face mask detection system to automatically classify masked and unmasked faces, achieving a detection accuracy of above 95% and proving its efficacy for real-time surveillance to minimize the risk of COVID-19 transmission in public settings. In⁽¹²⁾, proposed a hybrid deep transfer learning approach that used pre-trained models such as ResNet and MobileNet to improve the accuracy of mask detection to a level of accuracy of about 99% on standard datasets, thus proving its robustness even when trained on a few samples. In⁽¹³⁾, designed a real-time social distancing surveillance system that used YOLOv3 for person detection and DeepSORT tracking to compute interpersonal distances, thus ensuring accurate detection with high precision and making way for the automated detection of distancing violations in crowded environments. In⁽¹⁴⁾, proposed an end-to-end deep learning-based compliance system that combined face mask detection and social distance surveillance, thus ensuring accuracy of above 98% in mask detection and successful distance violation detection, thus providing a complete solution for the enforcement of COVID-19 safety protocols. In⁽¹⁵⁾, proposed a two-stage object detection architecture in low-light conditions by combining image enhancement methods and YOLOv7, which improved mean average precision from 0.49 to 0.574⁽¹⁶⁾. Hybrid structured document extraction models based on BERT-CRF sequence labeling, knowledge graphs, and reasoning systems reached a macro-average F1-score of 0.850, proving better performance in format-variant government documents. The multimodal architecture for document retrieval using feature fusion through the Transformer and reinforcement learning brought about great advances in the accuracy and speed of retrieval⁽¹⁷⁾. In-depth analysis of object detection models classified architectures into one-stage, two-stage, keypoint-based, and Transformer-based models, illustrating the trade-off between detection speed and localization accuracy⁽¹⁸⁾. In⁽¹⁹⁾, proposed a hybrid signature detection framework that combines deep learning based detection with post-processing refinement to improve localization in noisy scanned documents, achieving an F1-score above 90% with reduced false positives and establishing a reliable baseline for automated document authentication.

Despite notable progress, signature localization in complex and realistic documents remains challenging. Many existing methods rely solely on single-stage or two-stage detectors and do not yet make the most of integrated architectures that maintain

efficiency and accuracy at the same time. Moreover, some research works consider uniform document layouts, while in real-life documents like certificates, challans, bills, and cheques, there are different layouts that make signature localization even more complicated. It is also difficult for systems to differentiate between handwritten signatures and other printed or graphic elements on documents. These need to be addressed in order to develop a robust system that can detect signatures from different kinds of documents confidently.

A key research gap in signature detection lies in handling diverse document formats under realistic conditions. Most of the existing literature on signature detection is based on fixed layouts or a single type of document. However, in real-world applications, signatures are found in a variety of documents such as certificates, challans, invoice bills, and cheques. But the detection of signatures in such varied documents has not been given much importance in the existing literature. Keeping in mind the real-world diversity, this research work has manually collected certificates, challans, and invoice bills from real sources, and the images of cheques were taken from Kaggle.

The motivation for this research arises to develop a system that, apart from being able to identify document elements correctly, is fast enough to facilitate use in real time. Through combining YOLOv8n with Faster R-CNN, the study seeks to bridge the gap by offering a compromise between speed and accuracy for reliable signature detection in semi-structured documents.

The contributions of this study are:

- We make use of our custom dataset captured on various kinds of documents including certificates, challans, invoice bills, and cheques.
- Our recommendation is a combination of YOLOv8n and Faster R-CNN for object detection in documents. Through the coupling of YOLOv8n speed with the accuracy of Faster R-CNN, the system gains an operational balance between efficiency and accuracy.
- The hybrid strategy works better than distinct single-stage or two-stage models, and its practicability in real document processing was confirmed.

Unlike traditional hybrid detection approaches where multiple detectors' outputs are simply combined followed by Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS), the proposed method involves an innovative integration of YOLOv8n and Faster R-CNN. In this approach, YOLOv8n is utilized for initial region proposal and filtering for identifying signature regions. These regions are further selectively refined using Faster R-CNN based on a confidence-guided dynamic switching strategy. Additionally, instead of directly combining bounding box detection, this approach involves feature refinement for dealing with issues like overlapping seals, interference from printed text, and variations in script languages. An enhanced approach to combining detection results based on confidence re-weighting and spatial agreement is utilized instead of traditional approaches like NMS. These innovations make this hybrid approach significantly different from existing approaches to signature detection.

This paper describes the relevance of signature detection and its application in the verification of semi-printed documents, along with an analysis of the current state of document image analysis techniques and the need for a better approach in dealing with semi-structured complex document layouts. The above sections gave the complete insights of the problem with respect to detection of signatures and rest of the paper is divided into the following sections: 2 Methodology, which introduces the proposed hybrid signature detection approach by combining YOLOv8n and Faster R-CNN for enhanced detection accuracy, precision, and robustness; 2.1 Dataset, which introduces the semi-printed document dataset employed in this research, including certificates, challans, cheques, and invoice bills amounting to 2,000 samples; 3 Results and Discussion, which analyses the performance of the proposed approach and demonstrates how the hybrid approach is effective in detecting signatures in different document layouts, thus proving its efficacy as a new approach that has not been considered in the past literature.

2 Methodology

The proposed hybrid approach for the detection of handwritten signatures in semi-printed documents. The scanned images of the documents are first normalized by resizing to have uniform input quality. The pre-processed images are then passed to YOLOv8n for fast detection of potential signature locations and the generation of high-confidence bounding boxes. The potential signature locations are then further refined by Faster R-CNN for better localization and elimination of false positives. The locations with low confidence and overlapping printed text are then re-evaluated for better confidence. The proposed method utilizes the strengths of YOLOv8n for fast detection and Faster R-CNN for accurate localization to properly identify handwritten signatures from printed text and graphics in complex semi-printed document layouts. The proposed method is shown in Figure 1.

Fig 1. Proposed hybrid model architecture

2.1 Dataset

While developing and testing our hybrid signature detection model, we gathered 2,000 scanned images of documents from real-world sources. Most of the documents, including certificates, challans, and invoice bills, were gathered manually so that we could gather images of different formats, layouts, and sizes that are commonly found in real-world applications. To further increase the size of the dataset, we also included images of cheques that were obtained from a publicly available Kaggle dataset. By combining documents that we gathered ourselves with those available in public sources, we were able to create a dataset that better reflects real-world variations and includes a wider range of document types. Each image was carefully examined, and the important regions, such as signatures and text comments, were manually marked. To ensure consistency, all images were resized to 640×640 pixels. We split the dataset into 70% for training, 20% for testing, and 10% for validation purposes so that we could accurately test the model and ensure that the results were reliable. The sample dataset is shown in Figure 2.

The statistical distribution and detailed information of the dataset are presented in Table 1.

2.2 Data Annotation

To achieve maximum quality training data, we did not employ automatic augmentation techniques but rather utilized manual annotation. Using the LabelMe tool, bounding boxes were drawn around the regions of interest, primarily the signature areas, and were labeled accordingly. The annotations were kept in two formats in order to support both detection models: YOLO-

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig 2. Sample dataset from (a) Certificates, (b) Challans, (c) Cheques, (d) Invoice bills

Table 1. Detailed information about the dataset

Document Types	Training	Validation	Test	Total Dataset
Certificates	350	50	100	500
Challans	350	50	100	500
Cheques	350	50	100	500
Invoice Bills	350	50	100	500
Total Dataset	1400	200	400	2000

format .txt files for YOLOv8n and COCO-style CSV files for Faster R-CNN. This method gave us greater label accuracy control and reduced inconsistency in the dataset. Mainly, the annotation process is done only for the training set not for the test set.

2.3 YOLOv8n: Single-Stage Detection Model

Role of YOLOv8n in the Hybrid Model: The Ultralytics YOLOv8n is the primary detection model employed in the hybrid model to rapidly identify the potential signature regions in semi-printed documents. The YOLOv8n is a one-stage detection model that uses a single forward pass to extract features and predict bounding boxes. The compact model (3.2M parameters, 72 layers) has C2f modules, a Spatial Pyramid Pooling Fast (SPPF) module for context aggregation, and a decoupled detection head for better classification and localization. The model was trained using the AdamW optimizer with SiLU activation and took approximately 5 hours of training time with 75–80% mAP (0.60-0.95). In the hybrid framework, YOLOv8n is used to quickly produce high-confidence candidate regions for further refinement.

Failure Cases of YOLOv8n: YOLOv8n can produce coarse bounding boxes or fail to detect signatures that are weak, overlapped with printed text, irregularly oriented, or small in size. It can also produce false positives when cursive printed text is similar to handwritten signatures.

2.4 Faster R-CNN: Two-Stage Detection Model

Role of Faster R-CNN in Hybrid Model: Faster R-CNN is the refinement stage of the hybrid model, which improves the localization accuracy and classification confidence of the proposed regions generated by YOLOv8n. The two-stage detection framework is comprised of a deep backbone network, a Region Proposal Network (RPN), and RoI pooling with bounding box regression. The model has approximately 41.8 million parameters and over 350 layers, and it is trained using the SGD optimizer and ReLU activation function. The training process took about 16 hours to complete, reaching a mean Average Precision (mAP) of 80% to 85% (0.60-0.95). The model provides more accurate and tighter bounding boxes, which is highly ideal for signature detection in complex document layouts.

Failure Cases of Faster R-CNN: Although Faster R-CNN is accurate, it is computationally intensive and slower than YOLOv8n. This model is not ideal for real-time signature detection due to its slowness. It may also fail in noisy document scans or when detecting faint signatures with very small sizes.

2.5 Hybrid Integration Strategy

The hybrid approach combines the fast region detection capability of YOLOv8n with the refinement capability of Faster R-CNN to strike a balance between speed and accuracy. First, the confident candidate regions are identified by YOLOv8n, which are then post-processed using Faster R-CNN to better localize and remove false positives. This two-step approach is helpful in reducing the presence of false negatives, improving the bounding boxes, and increasing robustness to noisy and complex document layouts.

The hybrid model (≈ 29.2 M parameters, ≈ 685 layers) trained for about 4 hours showed an enhanced detection performance of 85–95% mAP (0.60-0.95) with optimal processing time. Relative to other independent models, the hybrid model is more accurate than YOLOv8n and faster than Faster R-CNN, which is a better trade-off between accuracy and speed of detection.

In comparison to other traditional models like connected component analysis and template matching, the hybrid model provides improved flexibility in handling handwriting variations and complex document layouts. In addition, the independent performance evaluation with confidence threshold optimization, non-maximum suppression (NMS), cross-validation, and detailed error analysis for different document types provides an unbiased performance evaluation of the model.

2.5.1. Mathematical Notation and Definitions

Let an input document image be denoted as I . The detections produced by YOLOv8n and Faster R-CNN are represented as sets of bounding boxes along with their corresponding confidence scores.

$$D_y = \{(b_i^y, s_i^y)\}_{i=1}^N \quad (1)$$

$$D_f = \{(b_j^f, s_j^f)\}_{j=1}^M \quad (2)$$

where D_y and D_f denote the sets of detections obtained from YOLOv8n and Faster R-CNN, respectively; each detection consists of a bounding box and a confidence score. The bounding boxes $b_i^y = (x_1^i, y_1^i, x_2^i, y_2^i)$ and $b_j^f = (x_1^j, y_1^j, x_2^j, y_2^j)$ represent the i^{th} and j^{th} detections predicted by YOLOv8n and Faster R-CNN, respectively, where (x_1, y_1) and (x_2, y_2) denote the top-left and bottom-right coordinates of the bounding box.

The terms s_i^y and s_j^f represent the corresponding confidence scores associated with each detection. i and j denote the indices of detections, while N and M denote the total number of detections from YOLOv8n and Faster R-CNN, respectively.

Let T_c be the confidence threshold used for filtering low-confidence detections, and T_{nms} be the Intersection over Union (IoU) threshold used in Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) to eliminate overlapping bounding boxes.

2.5.2. Hybrid Fusion Formulation

To remove low-confidence detections, filtering is applied as follows:

$$D'_y = \{(b_i^y, s_i^y) \mid s_i^y \geq T_c\} \quad (3)$$

$$D'_f = \{(b_j^f, s_j^f) \mid s_j^f \geq T_c\} \quad (4)$$

The filtered detections are then combined:

$$D_{combined} = D'_y \cup D'_f \quad (5)$$

To eliminate redundant and overlapping detections, Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) is applied:

$$D_{final} = NMS(D_{combined}, T_{nms}) \quad (6)$$

2.5.2.1. Confidence Fusion . For overlapping detections referring to the same region, a combined confidence score can be defined as:

$$s_k = \alpha \cdot s_i^y + (1 - \alpha) \cdot s_j^f \quad (7)$$

Where s_k represents the fused confidence score of the k^{th} detection, and $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ controls the contribution of each model. In this work, equal weighting ($\alpha = 0.5$) can be assumed when both models provide comparable confidence estimates.

The proposed hybrid algorithm is illustrated in the Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: Hybrid Single-Stage and Two-Stage Integration for Document Element Detection**Input:** A dataset of heterogeneous document images comprising certificates, challans, cheques, and invoice bills.**Output:** Document images with detected elements highlighted using bounding boxes and confidence scores.for each image I in input set do

1. Read the input image: $Img \leftarrow Read(I)$
 2. Convert the image into tensor representation: $T \leftarrow TransformToTensor(Img)$
 3. Initialize empty sets:
 - $B \leftarrow \emptyset$ // set of bounding boxes
 - $S \leftarrow \emptyset$ // set of confidence scores
 4. Perform single-stage detection using YOLOv8n:
 - $(B_y, S_y) \leftarrow YOLOv8n_Detect(Img)$
 5. Filter YOLOv8n detections based on confidence threshold T_c :
 - for each detection i in B_y do
 - if $S_y(i) \geq T_c$ then
 - $B \leftarrow B \cup B_y(i)$
 - $S \leftarrow S \cup S_y(i)$
 - end if
 - end for
 6. Perform two-stage detection using Faster R-CNN:
 - $(B_f, S_f) \leftarrow FRCNN_Detect(T)$
 7. Filter Faster R-CNN detections based on confidence threshold T_c :
 - for each detection j in B_f do
 - if $S_f(j) \geq T_c$ then
 - $B \leftarrow B \cup B_f(j)$
 - $S \leftarrow S \cup S_f(j)$
 - end if
 - end for
 8. if $B \neq \emptyset$, then
 - (a) Construct a unified detection from both models.
 - (b) Apply Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS):
 - $K \leftarrow NMS(B, S, T_{nms})$
 - (c) Obtain final detections:
 - $B_{final} \leftarrow B[K]$
 - $S_{final} \leftarrow S[K]$
 - (d) Overlay bounding boxes on the original document image.
 - (e) Assign confidence score to each detected region:
 - Label \leftarrow "Signature (score)"
 - (f) Save the resulting document image with highlighted detections.
 - else
 - Proceed to the next image.
 - end if
- end for
return all processed document images.

3 Results and Discussion

The proposed hybrid approach was applied to real-world semi-printed documents like certificates, challans, cheques, and invoice bills to overcome the challenge of signature detection in semi-printed documents containing a mixture of printed and handwritten text. The proposed approach leverages the strength of YOLOv8n's fast detection ability and the refinement ability of Faster R-CNN to detect signature regions in semi-printed documents, even when the layout is complex with overlapping

text and noise. The experimental results indicate that the proposed approach is effective in overcoming the challenges of false detection and localization in semi-printed documents.

3.1 Experimental Results

For analyzing the performance and reliability of our hybrid signature detection scheme, we have conducted experiments on four classes of real documents: challans, cheques, certificates, and invoice bills. The reason for choosing these classes is that they have different document structure and complexity. The hybrid model's final results are shown in Figure 3.

Fig 3. Final Result of the hybrid Model (a) Resultant Images (b) Cropped Images from Resultant Images

3.1.1. Protocol for Experimental Validation and Evaluation

In order to provide an impartial evaluation of the results, the dataset was carefully split into training, validation, and testing sets, with the test set never being used for training purposes. Measures were taken to prevent any kind of data leakage occurs since there would be no overlap in the images or annotations in any way among the three sets.

For the purpose of making the result evaluation more robust, several trials were conducted and cross-validation techniques were utilized. All performance results presented hereafter represent an average value with variance provided to demonstrate the stability of the evaluation process.

Despite the achieved high precision scores, further analysis of the results proved the consistency of the system performance when applied to various documents that differed in terms of layout and content structure. The performance results are represented by the average score with standard deviation.

3.2 Performance Metrics

For the present investigation, the effectiveness of the suggested hybrid architecture will be assessed on the basis of two important evaluation criteria: intersection over union and dice coefficient.

The intersection over union measure is used to express how much similarity the predicted bounding box shares with the signature’s true bounding box. The following mathematical representation can be made:

$$IoU = \frac{|B_p \cap B_g|}{|B_p \cup B_g|} \tag{8}$$

Where B_p represents the predicted bounding box and B_g denotes the ground truth bounding box.

Dice Coefficient is used to determine the level of similarity between the predicted and actual signatures. The calculation is done using twice the value of the intersection area divided by the sum of the two areas.

$$Dice\ Coefficient = \frac{2 * |B_p \cap B_g|}{|B_p| + |B_g|} \tag{9}$$

Precision is calculated by comparing the amount of true positive detections out of all the detections made. Here, an IoU value above a certain threshold qualifies as a correct detection.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \tag{10}$$

Where TP indicates the number of true positive detections ($IoU \geq threshold$) and FP indicates the number of false positive detections.

Recall is the measurement of the capability of the model in detecting all the existing signatures in the document.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \tag{11}$$

Where FN is the number of missed signature regions (true signature regions that were not identified by the model).

The F1-Score is used to balance the values of precision and recall, particularly where the distribution of classes is skewed.

$$F1\ -\ Score = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \tag{12}$$

Accuracy represents the overall correctness of the model in detecting both signature and non-signature regions.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \tag{13}$$

Where TN represents the true negative detections.

All of these steps combined provide an average measurement of how far the hybrid model localizes and detects signatures on various document types such as certificates, challans, invoice bills, and cheques.

The performance metrics of the hybrid model are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Performance metrics of the hybrid model

Document Types	IoU (avg)	Dice Coefficient	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Accuracy
Certificates	0.6328	0.7208	1.0000	0.8462	0.9167	0.8462
Challans	0.6735	0.7676	1.0000	0.8400	0.9130	0.8400
Invoice bills	0.8526	0.9194	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
Cheques	0.8928	0.9428	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000

The hybrid model performed well on the given set of 2,000 semi-printed documents, with an average accuracy of 92.15% and an F1-score of 95.74%. The accuracy was highest in cheques and invoice bills due to their organized structure, and in certificates and challans, which had more variability and noise, still produced good results. The signatures were detected correctly with only minor errors in cases where the signatures were weak or overlapping. The hybrid system performed better than the individual approaches in terms of reducing false positives and improving localization accuracy, thus proving its effectiveness in accurately detecting signatures.

3.3 Comprehensive Model Comparison and Selection

As an attempt at validating the proposed approach, various experiments have been performed using several models for document element detection, ranging from single stage models such as YOLOv8n, YOLOv9, YOLOv10, YOLOv11, YOLOv12, and YOLO-SAM, two stage models like R-CNN, Fast R-CNN, and Faster R-CNN, and transformer based models like DETR, RT-DETR, and RF-DETR.

From the results, it is clear that majority of the mentioned models exhibit poor performance when used to detect elements in the document dataset, with a relatively lower mean average precision (mAP) of approximately 20-25 percent. Specifically, transformer based models such as DETR, RT-DETR, and RF-DETR yielded lower detection accuracies, mainly because they depend on huge volumes of data as well as lengthy training durations.

For the case of single stage models, YOLOv8n performed better than the other models, owing to its efficiency in capturing useful features in the document image. As regards the two stage models, Faster R-CNN yielded comparatively better results, due to improved localization abilities and ability to reliably detect small signature regions in the document image.

From this experiment, YOLOv8n and Faster R-CNN have been chosen as the basis of the proposed hybrid framework. This fusion of models enables the model to take advantage of fast detection and accurate detection at the same time.

The detailed test conducted shows that the proposed hybrid model is empirically based and outperforms single detector models in document element detection.

3.4 Component Contribution Analysis

Table 3 presents the quantitative comparison in terms of mAP, training time, and model complexity. It could be seen from the table that YOLOv8n is able to detect objects more rapidly and with less computational costs whereas Faster R-CNN detects objects accurately but takes a lot of time in the process. Hybrid model successfully integrates their respective strengths and becomes more efficient than other approaches.

Along with the quantitative comparison, the qualitative comparison was conducted via visual analysis, as illustrated in Figure 4. YOLOv8n usually detects coarser bounding boxes along with some false positives. However, Faster R-CNN manages to detect finer bounding boxes but may fail to capture some areas of interest. Consequently, the hybrid approach manages to achieve better results.

Besides, the effect of different confidence and IoU thresholds during the testing phase was analyzed. In particular, it has been found out that thresholding plays an important role when it comes to achieving the balance between precision and recall, whereas Non-Maximum Suppression helps eliminate redundant detections. All the experiments prove that the proposed hybrid model has become more efficient because of the joint effect of two algorithms on region detection and its refinement.

3.5 Model Comparison

YOLOv8n was faster in detecting signatures, but sometimes it missed the minute details. On the other hand, Faster R-CNN provided more accurate results, but it took longer to process. When both methods were combined, the hybrid model was more consistent and dependable in its results for different types of documents. The comparison between the models are shown in Figure 4 and Table 3.

In earlier studies, R-CNN-based architectures showed the ability to detect handwritten signatures in complex layouts effectively⁽¹⁾, and benchmarking systems showed F1-scores of above 90% on structured datasets⁽²⁾. Automated cheque processing systems showed an accuracy of about 94%⁽³⁾, and hybrid CNN-HOG methods showed an accuracy of about 92.6%⁽⁴⁾. More recent YOLO-based approaches focused on real-time processing, which showed high speed along with accuracy of about 85-90%⁽⁵⁾,⁽⁶⁾,⁽⁷⁾,⁽⁸⁾, while segmentation-based methods like Mask R-CNN showed good localization with pixel-level accuracy of about 90%⁽⁹⁾.

The findings of the study are in agreement with the above-mentioned observations for individual models, where YOLOv8n gave a faster detection with moderate accuracy (75-80% mAP), and Faster R-CNN gave a higher accuracy (80-85% mAP) with increased computational time. But the proposed hybrid model gives better results than the above models as it gives a mAP of

Fig 4. Model comparison (a) Detected Images, (b) Detection of the YOLOv8n Model, (c) Detection of the Faster R-CNN Model, (d) Detection of the Hybrid Model

Table 3. Model comparison

Model	Architecture/Design	Applications	Opti- mizer(s)	Activa- tion Function	Param- e- ters(M)	Lay- ers	Train- ing Time	mAP (60:95)
YOLOv8n	One-Stage CNN (c2f Block, SSPE, Decoupled Head)	Real-time Signature Detection & fast processing	AdamW	SiLU	3.2M	72	5 hrs	75-80%
Faster R-CNN	Two-stage CNN (Backbone + RPN + RoI Head)	High accuracy signature detection in dense layouts	SGD	ReLU	41.8M	350+	16 hrs	80-85%
Hybrid Model	YOLOv8n + Faster R-CNN (YOLO backbone + RCNN proposal refinement)	Balanced accuracy & speed for document automation	AdamW + SGD	SiLU + ReLU	29.2M	685	4 hrs	85-95%

85-95% along with an average accuracy of 92.15% and F1-score of 95.74%. This clearly indicates that the hybrid approach of fast region detection and accurate refinement is efficient in enhancing the accuracy and robustness of document detection.

In comparison with the existing studies, the proposed approach has obvious advantages in dealing with semi-printed documents containing both handwritten and printed data, which are more complex than the structured datasets used in the existing reports. In fact, many existing approaches are evaluated on clean and well-aligned data, while the current study deals with the real-world challenges such as noise, overlapping text, layout variations, and different signature styles, and yet the approach still keeps robust performance.

The originality of the research work lies in the hybrid integration method, wherein a lightweight single-stage detector is combined with a two-stage refinement model. Contrary to the previous methods that concentrated either on speed or accuracy, the research work presents a detection and refinement method in a sequential manner that tends to minimize the false positives, improve the accuracy of the bounding boxes, and increase the consistency of the overall detection. Additionally, the inclusion of a diverse dataset containing certificates, challans, cheques, and invoice bills increases the ability of the model to generalize well.

4 Conclusion

This study proposes a hybrid signature detection system by combining YOLOv8n and Faster R-CNN to overcome the difficulties posed by semi-structured and semi-printed documents. With the hybrid approach, the system was able to reach a total accuracy of 92.15%, thus achieving a perfect balance between computational complexity and detection accuracy. The experimental outcome showed that the system performed efficiently on various types of documents such as certificates, challans, bills, and cheques. The outcome confirmed that the proposed hybrid system is practical and has the potential for real-time verification. Compared to the performance of other models, which are likely to be sensitive to layout changes, the hybrid system improves the accuracy of signature detection areas with less preprocessing. This paper fills the theoretical gap between object detection models and their applications in document analysis.

In future work, we plan to expand the dataset to cover more challenging and diverse real-world scenarios. The aim is to enable end-to-end automation by integrating the framework into a comprehensive document analysis system. This will be used in digital forensics, archival digitization, and automated form processing, while also ensuring a stable processing rate for industrial and legal documents.

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